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Research Article

To Study Prescribing Pattern and Utilization Pattern of Various Drugs in Stroke Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The increasing incidence of stroke has emerged as a significant public health issue, requiring attention from neurologists. Neuro protective drugs are a cornerstone of treatment, but there is a lack of well-defined research on stroke's clinical symptomatology and medication usage in India, highlighting the need for further studies in this area. This study states that the prescription patterns of drugs used in the management and prevention of stroke. **Methods:** Single centered prospective observational study in patients with stroke disease in Narasaraopet. They were randomly approach by case reports to ashok neuro care hospital in Narsaraopet, Palnadu. **Results:** A total of 94 patients were studied over a six months period, with 56.3% males and 43.6% females. The highest incidence of stroke was observed in the 40-59 year age group. Ischemic stroke accounted for 65.9% of cases, while hemorrhagic stroke comprised 23.42%, yielding a ratio of 2.09. The most common stroke risk factors were hypertension, dyslipidemia, and diabetes. The most commonly prescribed medications for hospitalized stroke patients were antihypertensives, followed by hypolipidemic agents and antiplatelet drugs. **Conclusion:** The study emphasizes the importance of drug utilization patterns in promoting rational prescribing and analysis. However, it was limited by the lack of follow-up, hindering the evaluation of complications and their management. In conclusion, effective management of risk factors and adherence to treatment guidelines can mitigate severity and enhance prognostic outcomes. Early identification of risk factors and treatment patterns is crucial for ensuring high-quality patient care.

INTRODUCTION

Rational Drug Use (RDU) is a vital component to deliver better healthcare to patients and the

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community. Rational drug use is defined as patients taking drugs as per their clinical need, in a dose according to individual need for a sufficient period, at the lowest cost to the patient and community. Ensuring patients' safety has always been a crucial element of health and medical care for patients in any healthcare setting.¹ Irrational use of drugs can rise mortality and morbidity rate, particularly among chronic disease patients. It also develops adverse drug reactions. The World Health Organization (WHO)-International Network for the Rational Use of Drugs (INRUD) developed a set of core drug use indicators that are useful to study the patterns of drug prescribing in the hospital settings and to measure the rational drug use pattern.² Proper drug selection, dosage form, and route of administration are key to achieving optimal therapeutic outcomes in stroke management.³ Stroke, or cerebrovascular accident occurs due to impaired blood flow to the brain, potentially leading to death if not promptly and treated.⁴ Stroke is the second leading cause of global mortality and a major contributor to long-term disability in adults with 90% of survivors experiencing residual impairments.⁵ The risk of stroke increases with age (particularly after 55), obesity, hypertension, diabetes, atrial fibrillation, and dyslipidemia.⁶ Hypertension, diabetes, smoking, and obesity are significant risk factors for stroke in the Indian population, with proper management reducing the associated risks.⁷ Stroke is a major public health issue, typically managed by neurologists, often in specialized stroke units during the acute phase. Medical and surgical interventions are crucial for managing elevated intracranial pressure (ICP). Clinical trials have demonstrated the effectiveness of antiplatelet agents and oral anticoagulants in preventing stroke.⁸ Stroke management should be individualized, with proper drug utilization being essential. In developing countries, challenges such as inadequate healthcare infrastructure,

insufficient government control over drug supply, and the illegal free availability of drugs exacerbate issues in stroke care.⁹ Effective drug treatment involves selecting appropriate medications, including thrombolytics, anticoagulants, antihypertensives (e.g., ACE inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor blockers, diuretics), lipid-lowering agents (statins), antiplatelet drugs (aspirin, clopidogrel), and neuroprotective agents. The WHO emphasizes the importance of considering medical, social, and economic factors in drug utilization.¹⁰ The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the medication prescribing pattern and utilization pattern of various drugs in stroke patients.¹¹

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design:

The study was conducted at Ashok Neuro Care Super Speciality Hospital in Narasaraopet, Palnadu in 6 months period of time.

Study method:

Patient information collected from patient case sheets and required data entered in data collection forms. The data collected based on various parameters like Age, Gender, Type of stroke, Risk factors, Group of drugs, Types of drugs.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table-1. Demographic profile analysis

S. No	Age	Male	Female	Total	Percentage
1.	20-39	13	9	22	23.40%
2.	40-59	21	19	40	42.55%
3.	60-79	10	8	18	19.16%
4.	>80	9	5	14	14.89%

Table-2. Type of stroke

S. No	Type Of Stroke	No. Of Patiets	Percentage
1.	Ischemic stroke	62	65.95%
2.	Haemorrhagic stroke	22	23.42%

3.	Sub arachnoid haemorrhagic stroke	10	10.63%
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Table-3. Risk factors and Comorbidities associated with stroke

S. No	Risk Factors	No. Of Patients	Percentage
1.	High blood pressure	64	32.65%
2.	Dys lipidemia	40	20.40%
3.	Diabetes mellitus	37	18.87%
4.	Smoking history	22	11.22%
5.	Associated cardiac problems	18	9.18%

6.	Alcohol	10	5.10%
7.	Obesity	5	2.55%

Table-4. Groups of drugs prescribed in stroke patients

S. No	Group Of Drugs	No. Of Patient	Percentage
1.	Antihypertensive agents	75	26.69%
2.	Lipid lowering agents	62	22.06%
3.	Antiplatelet agents	72	25.65%
4.	Cerebral activators	39	13.87%
5.	Anticoagulants	28	9.96%
6.	Thrombolytics	5	1.77%

Table-5. Types of drugs prescribed in stroke patients

S. No	Type Of Drug	No. Of Patients	Percentage
1.	Anticoagulants: Enoxaparin	40	43.02%
	Heparin	27	29.03%
	Dalteparin	14	15.05%
	Foundoparinux	8	8.60%
	Oral anticoagulant	4	4.30%
2.	Antiplatelets: Aspirin	84	45.16%
	Clopidogrel	69	37.09%
	Aspirin+ Clopidogrel	28	15.05%
	Aspirin+ Dipyridamole	5	2.68%
3.	Tissue Plasminogen Activators: Alteplase	5	5.3%
4.	Antihypertensives: Beta blockers	75	24.9%
	Alpha-2 adrenergic agonist	28	9.3%
	Alpha-2 adrenergic blocker	13	4.3%
	Mixed alpha+ beta blockers	22	7.30%
	Calcium channel blockers	65	21.5%
	Angiotensin converting enzymes	52	17.2%

	AT ₁ receptors	32	10.6%
	Diuretics	14	4.6%
5.	Lipid Lowering Agents: Atorvastatin	69	48.9%
	Rosuvastatin	42	29.7%
	Fenofibrate	22	15.6%
	Ezetimibe	8	5.6%
6.	Cerebral Activators: Citicholine	72	72.00%
	Piracetam	19	19.00%
	Edaravone	7	7.00%
	Cerebro protein hydrosylate	2	2.00%
7.	Antibiotics: Amoxicillin+ Clavulanic acid, Clindamycin, Ceftriaxone, Piperacillin+ Tazobactam, Metrozyl, Vncomycin, Meropenem	125	100%
8.	Antiepileptics: Phenytoin	67	74.4%
	Valproate	18	20.0%
	Levitiracetam	5	5.5%
9.	Osmotic Diuretics: Mannitol	72	57.6%
	3% NS	21	16.8%
	Glycerol	32	25.6%
10.	Antipsychotics: Quetiapine, Haloperidol, Midazolam	79	84.0%
11.	Antiacids: Esmoprazole, Pantoprazole, Omeprazole, Rantak, Domperidone	245	100%

4. CONCLUSION:

The study emphasizes the significance of understanding drug utilization patterns to encourage rational prescribing and analysis. However, its limitation lies in the absence of follow-up, which hindered the assessment of complications and their management. In conclusion, effective risk factor management and

adherence to treatment guidelines can reduce severity and improve prognostic outcomes. Early identification of risk factors and treatment patterns is crucial for delivering high-quality patient care.

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